

OCEAN ICE News – October 2025

OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to October's edition of OCEAN ICE News. We're excited to bring you the latest updates from the OCEAN ICE community.

In this issue, you'll meet our featured researcher of the month and catch up on key activities, OCEAN ICE at AAORIA, A report summarising the OCEAN ICE Annual project meeting, highlighting August and September's Climate Coffee. We have some upcoming Climate Coffee's that you can register for in October and November. Don't forget to mark your calendars for the upcoming events where OCEAN ICE will be represented.

We hope you enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to sharing more in November!

Researcher in the Spotlight: Yixi Zheng

Check out our latest 'Researcher in the Spotlight' feature on Yixi Zheng, a postdoctoral researcher at the British Antarctic Survey specialising in Antarctic physical oceanography

Read the feature on Yixi [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN ICE Activities

OCEAN ICE Presented at All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance (AAORIA)

OCEAN ICE was recently presented at the All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance (AAORIA) Andrew Meijers delivered a talk on the outcomes of OCEAN ICE and future research needs, specifically highlighting the need for synchronous and coordinated multinational efforts to understand the rapidly changing Antarctic and Southern Ocean. He showcased the new observations achieved by OCEAN ICE, its modelling improvements and the resulting data products and assessments.

This year AAORIA held its forum in Brussels, and as part of this held a polar side event on the 24th of September, hosted by the European Polar Board to highlight European efforts under global frameworks for polar research.

Read the full article [here](#).

OCEAN ICE Annual Project Meeting 2025: Collaboration, Progress and Future Priorities

The OCEAN ICE consortium gathered for its third Annual Project Meeting from 15-16 September 2025 at the Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI) in Copenhagen, with many joining online. The meeting was followed by a joint workshop with the Southern Ocean Observing System (SOOS), as well as workshops dedicated to early career researchers (ECRs) and future collaborative initiatives. The week of events brought together a vibrant international community of Southern Ocean and cryosphere experts, reinforcing interdisciplinary collaboration and scientific momentum as the project enters its final year.

Work package leaders, co-leaders and representatives outlined achievements and detailed plans for the final 12 months. The meeting also helped strengthen collaboration across work packages, ensuring alignment with long-term objectives.

Catch up with the full article [here](#).

OCEAN ICE at EPOC Annual Meeting

Earlier this week I joined the EPOC annual meeting that met in Bergen, Norway. Elaine McDonagh from WP5 introduced OCEAN ICE to the group and enjoyed listening to the science talks. While the focus of EPOC is in the North and OCEAN ICE is in the South there are overlaps. These include the EPOC analysis of heat and freshwater that reaches to the south Atlantic SAMBA array to which OCEAN ICE is adding instruments and undertaking an analysis of multi decadal regional change the bi-polar interaction of sea-ice formation and its interaction with deep water formation: a key part of OCEAN ICE and an emerging metric in EPOC.

OCEAN ICE Climate coffee – August

Climate Coffee with Amina Ben Salah on A Copula-Based Approach to Explore Climate-Driven Ocean Variability In the Gibraltar Strait.

What this webinar is about This study investigates the impact of climate change on small pelagic fish stocks by modelling the complex relationships between sea surface temperature (SST) and chlorophyll-a (Chl-a) concentration. These two variables serve as key indicators of oceanic conditions that influence the abundance of marine organisms. A copula-based modelling approach is employed to assess these dependencies using satellite-derived data from MODISA and climate

hindcast models. The analysis focuses on the Strait of Gibraltar, a biologically productive and climate-sensitive region. It considers seasonal variations by analyzing the March–April–May (MAM) and September–October–November (SON) periods. The marginal distributions and copulas are first fitted to historical observations, then applied to model data. A multivariate bias correction method is used to enhance the model simulations. This framework provides a foundation for understanding long-term changes in ocean dynamics and their potential effects on fisheries.

The study has been published recently: <https://link.springer.com/article/10...>

This presentation is available on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/16964854>

Our speaker Amina Ben Salah is a Moroccan PhD candidate in her third year under the MICODIR project. Her research focuses on modelling small pelagic fish stocks using advanced statistical methods, particularly the application of copula-based approaches to study climate–marine ecosystem interactions

28 August 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online

Amina Ben Salah (UAE)
**A Copula-Based Approach to Explore
Climate-Driven Ocean Variability in the
Strait of Gibraltar**

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

OCEAN ICE Climate coffee – September

Climate Coffee with Audrey Minière on Estimating ocean warming: Challenges & recommendations for robust assessment

Human-induced emissions have driven the Earth into an energy imbalance, resulting in the accumulation of excess heat within the climate system. Approximately 90% of this surplus energy is absorbed by the global ocean, causing ocean warming and making Ocean Heat Content (OHC) a key indicator of climate change. However, accurately quantifying OHC remains difficult due to the evolving observing system, significant methodological differences, and varying data processing approaches. Despite its essential role in climate monitoring, there are currently no established guidelines for calculating the OHC indicator. In this presentation, we review the main challenges in estimating OHC and emphasize the urgent need for a coordinated international effort to establish the first set of recommendations for OHC assessment. A robust and consistent methodology is crucial for tracking past, present, and future climate change, and for addressing the pressing question of global warming acceleration. Our speaker Audrey Minière works at Ecole Normale Supérieure (ENS). "I am a postdoctoral researcher at the Laboratoire de Météorologie Dynamique

(ENS, Paris), working on ocean warming. My research focuses on its spatial and temporal distribution and its estimation using a variety of observational data, including in situ measurements, satellite observations, and reanalyses. I work with Prof. Sabrina Speich and Dr. Karina von Schuckmann".

25 September 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online

Audrey Minière (ENS)

**Estimating ocean warming: challenges
and recommendations for robust
assessment**

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

OCEAN ICE Deliverables and Milestones submitted

The OCEAN ICE community has been busy recently submitting various deliverables and milestones:

- M11 [‘Addition of MicroCAT to the SAMBA array’](#)
- D7.5 [‘Infrastructure design v.2.0’](#)
- D7.8 [‘OCEAN ICE data catalogue system’](#)
- D7.3 [‘Data Management Plan v.3.0’](#)
- D10.3 [‘Particles track from model and observations: A contribution to the OCEAN ICE work packages WP1 and WP2’](#)
- D4.2 [‘Freshwater fluxes between 2000 and 2300 with robust UQ’](#)
- D5.1 [‘Mooring dataset from South Sandwich Trench’](#)
- D3.4 [‘Feasibility study into ice sheet-ocean model initialisation’](#)

The progress and results of OCEAN ICE are published in deliverables and milestone reports.

In order to keep up with the OCEAN ICE deliverables and milestones, visit our [website](#) and stay tuned on our social media channels.

Upcoming Events

Climate Coffee

We have an upcoming Climate Coffee in August, September, October and November, make sure you register for all of them through the link on [OCEAN ICE](#).

Climate Coffee with Blanca Fernández Álvarez on How Detection Frameworks Shape Our View of 2024's Mediterranean MHW

30 October 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

30 October 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET

Online

Blanca Fernández-Álvarez (IMEDEA-CSIC)

How Detection Frameworks Shape Our View of 2024's Mediterranean Marine Heatwaves

Danish Meteorological Institute

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Climate Coffee with Natacha Legrix De La Salle on Surface and Subsurface Compound MHW and Biogeochemical Extremes

Under Climate Change.

27 November 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

27 November 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET

Online

Natacha Legrix De La Salle (Univ. Liverpool)

Surface and Subsurface Compound Marine Heatwave and Biogeochemical Extremes Under Climate Change

Danish Meteorological Institute

OCEAN:ICE

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Happening Soon

OCEAN ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 29th – 31st October, [Nordic Branch of IGS Meeting](#), Copenhagen Denmark
- 18th November 2025, Policy Briefing, Brussels, Belgium
- 9th – 12th Feb 2026, [Open Science Conference](#), New Zealand
- 22nd – 27th February 2025, [Ocean Sciences Meeting](#), Glasgow, Scotland
- 9th – 13th March 2026, [CMIP 2026 Meeting](#), Kyoto, Japan

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

Are you following us on Social Media?

Stay up to date with OCEAN ICE on our following channels:

www.ocean-ice.eu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>

https://twitter.com/OCEANICE_EU

<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

<https://www.facebook.com/OCEANICEEU/>

[OCEAN ICE \(@oceaniceeu.bsky.social\) — Bluesky](#)

Who is OCEAN ICE?

OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

OCEAN:ICE

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